

THE PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF ASCORBIC ACID*

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Fellows of the Indian Chemical Society, Ladies and Gentlemen,

I would, in the first place, take this opportunity of offering my best thanks to you for the honour which you conferred on me a year ago by electing me as your President. This is the highest gift which the chemists of India can offer to one of their Fellow-workers and I am very grateful to you all for your kind appreciation.

The Council expressed the wish sometime ago, that it was desirable that the old practice of the President addressing the Fellows at the annual general meeting should be revived ; I therefore make no apology in speaking to you on a subject in which I have been interested for some time.

Ascorbic acid, since its isolation in the pure state by Szent-Györgi and the elucidation of its constitution by the Birmingham School led by Haworth has been a material of such absorbing interest to all chemists that it was considered worth while to investigate its physico-chemical properties in detail. The constitution of ascorbic acid as given in (I) is now generally accepted as correct.

(I)

The hydroxy groups attached to the doubly linked carbon atoms have the remarkable property that they are both capable of easy oxidation and stepwise dissociation into H-ions. When ascorbic acid was first isolated, it was found that "it avidly took up oxygen" and legitimately suggested that by its power of reversible oxidation, it could function as an oxygen carrier. Kellie and Zilva¹ however proved that if ascorbic acid were dissolved in pure water distilled from quartz vessels, it was as stable as in the solid form. This observation was confirmed by Barron and co-workers² who found that recrystallised natural ascorbic acid

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free from the last traces of copper, if dissolved in the purest water, did not undergo any auto-oxidation up to p_H values 7.6. We have, however, found³ that the behaviour of synthetic acid is different as regards its stability. Carefully purified synthetic ascorbic acid, when dissolved in purest water, gave results which did not agree with the observations of Zilva, Barron and co-workers. If auto-oxidation was estimated in a Warburg apparatus, oxidation between 70–90% took place in an hour within the p_H range 5.8 and 7.2. There are two possibilities—either our system contained traces of copper which is the most active catalyst known for this auto-oxidation or that pure ascorbic acid is capable of auto-oxidation but that the natural material used by Zilva and Barron contained traces of a very powerful protective agent.

Our reaction mixtures were accordingly tested for copper by rubeanic acid, and for copper and iron by sodium diethyldithiocarbamate with negative results. It might be contended that concentrations of copper, even lower than those detectable by these micro-reagents, could act catalytically. It was found that if copper salt were actually added to our solutions of ascorbic acid, so as to make its concentration of the order of 10^{-6} mols per litre, the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid is not perceptibly accelerated at p_H 7. Further evidence that the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid is not catalysed by copper when present in concentrations which could not be detected by rubeanic acid is obtained by the study of the action of potassium iodide on these systems.

The reaction

proceeds to completion towards the right if the iodine set free is used up to oxidise ascorbic acid present in excess. The solubility product of CuI is of the order of 10^{-12} ; hence in a solution having a concentration of KI equal to 10^{-3} g. mol per litre, the concentration of Cu^{++} ion in presence of excess of ascorbic acid would be of the order of 10^{-9} . If copper were responsible for the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid, KI would act as a retarding agent. KI in concentrations of the order of 10^{-3} g. mol per litre was found to have absolutely no action on the auto-oxidation of synthetic ascorbic acid which, therefore, is capable of spontaneous auto-oxidation. The conclusion becomes irresistible that the natural ascorbic acid used by Zilva, Barron (*et al*) contained traces of powerful protective agent. As to the exact nature of this protective system, significance attaches to the observation of Birch and Dann⁴ that ascorbic acid and glutathione commonly occur in conjunction with one another.

They, in fact, described ascorbic acid and glutathione as linked factors in one system of oxidation in the animal cell. The reduction of dehydro-ascorbic acid by glutathione has been observed to be fairly rapid and is considered to be of considerable biological significance. Hence it was surmised that glutathione even in traces might protect ascorbic acid from auto-oxidation. Table I shows that sulphhydryl compounds, even in their oxidised form, can inhibit the auto-oxidation of synthetic ascorbic acid when present in order of concentrations 10^{-4} to $10^{-8} M$.

TABLE I.

Ascorbic acid = 0.004 g. = 260 c.mm. O_2 . Soln. = 3 c.mm. Temp. = 30°. Air = 48 c. mm.

Inhibitor.	Molar conc. of (A)	ps.	C. mm. of O_2 absorbed in			% of ascorbic acid left after 180 min.	
			60 min.	120 min.	180 min.		
Reduced glutathione	—	5.2	70	125	—		
	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	5.2	0	5	—		
	—	8.2	125	205	—		
	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	8.2	20	20	—		
	—	6.9	110	175	230	11	
	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$	6.9	20	45	50	81	
Oxidised glutathione	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	6.9	60	65	70	75	
	$1 \cdot 10^{-6}$	6.9	120	155	190	27	
	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	6.9	20	40	45	85	
	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	6.9	5	0	20	92	
	Cystein	$2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	6.9	0	10	15	97
		$2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	6.9	0	5	5	98
$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$		6.9	0	0	5	98	
$2 \cdot 10^{-7}$		6.9	80	160	185	28	
Cystin	$14 \cdot 10^{-4}$	6.9	25	25	30	88	
	$14 \cdot 10^{-6}$	6.9	20	25	20	92	
Sulphuretted hydrogen	$14 \cdot 10^{-5}$	6.9	0	0	10	96	
	$14 \cdot 10^{-6}$	6.9	75	120	185	28	

Similar results were obtained with thiolactic acid (*vide* Table IA).

TABLE IA.

Soln. = 1.2 c. mm. Air = 16.8 c. mm. Ascorbic acid = $1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ M. Temp. = 28°.

p_H . (Phosphate).	Conc. of thiolaetic acid.	C. mm. 30 min.	of oxygen absorbed in		
			60 min.	90 min.	120 min.
5.2	—	16	—	34	37
5.2	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mol.	17	—	34	37
5.2	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0	0	0	0
6.0	—	24	36	49	60
6.0	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	12	16	19	24
6.0	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0	0	0	0
7.0	—	61	86	103	—
7.0	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	64	82	—	—
7.0	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0	0	0	—
8.0	—	—	91	108	—
8.0	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	64	96	110	—
8.0	$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0	0	0	—

The action of mercuric chloride on these systems yields very interesting results. When added to ascorbic acid solutions at p_H 7, it has no effect whatever on the velocity of auto-oxidation. $HgCl_2$, however, easily combines with sulphhydryl compounds giving products which are extremely insoluble; hence it is to be expected that the protective action of sulphhydryl compounds may be removed by the action of $HgCl_2$. Table II shows that this is actually the case.

TABLE II.

Ascorbic acid = $1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ mol. Temperature = 20°. $p_H = 7.0$.

Conc. of $HgCl_2$.	Conc. of SH.	C. mm. of oxygen absorbed in		
		30 min.	60 min.	90 min.
—	—	61	85	103
—	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mol. (Cystein)	0	0	0
—	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (Glutathione)	0	0	0
$1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mol.	—	60	84	107
—	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (Cystein)	65	80	102
—	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ (Glutathione)	32	46	—

It appears, therefore, that glutathione and cystein are inhibitors and copper is an accelerator of the spontaneous process of auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid. The interaction of these two factors will be clear from Table III.

TABLE III.

Cystein and Copper.

Ascorbic acid = 0.004 g. Temp. = 30°. Soln. = 3 c. mm. Air = 48 c. mm.

Amount of Cystein— HCl.	Amount of CuSO ₄ , 5H ₂ O.	Ca : cystein.	C. mm. of oxygen absorbed in		
			60 min.	120 min.	180 min.
—	—	—	120	185	220
—	75 × 10 ⁻⁶	—	140	165	180
1 × 10 ⁻⁵	15 × 10 ⁻⁶	1 : 1 mol.	0	0	0
1 × 10 ⁻⁵	37 × 10 ⁻⁶	5 : 2	—	180	225

The inhibition is complete when the ratio of copper to sulphhydryl compound is 1:1 and the protective action of sulphhydryl compound is removed when its ratio with copper is as 2:5. Besides the specific protective action of sulphhydryl compounds present in minute traces, it has been observed that various amino-acids can inhibit the oxidation of ascorbic acid when present in equivalent proportions.

Ascorbic acid is also found widely distributed in the plant kingdom. Giroud⁵ has found that the ascorbic acid content of plant leaves and tissues varies with their chlorophyll contents, is absent from plant grown in darkness and diminishes in leaves in autumn when chlorophyll disappears. Accordingly the inhibitory effect of chlorophyll on the auto-oxidation of ascorbic acid was studied. The purest samples of chlorophyll, α and β, were obtained from Prof. Stoll, and the results are indicated in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Conc. of ascorbic acid = 1 × 10⁻³. *p_H* = 7.0. Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of chlorophyll.	Chlorophyll-α.	C. m m. of oxygen absorbed after			
		0 min.	60 min.	120 min.	240 min.
Nil		0	65	86	92
1 × 10 ⁻⁴		0	0	0	0
2 × 10 ⁻⁵		0	45	65	68
	Chlorophyll-β.				
Nil		0	65	86	92
2 × 10 ⁻³		0	0	0	0
2 × 10 ⁻⁴		0	0	0	0
2 × 10 ⁻⁵		0	69	78	84

It is clear that chlorophyll at concentrations of the order of 10^{-4} completely protects ascorbic acid from oxidation by oxygen. It thus appears that wherever ascorbic acid is found in the plant and animal kingdom, nature always associates it with materials which prevent its oxidative destruction.

It has already been noted that if ascorbic acid were to function as a carrier of oxygen in the cell, it should be capable of reversible oxidation and reduction according to the equation

The thermodynamic equation for the electromotive force of such a system should be

$$E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{F} \cdot p_{\text{H}^+} + \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{[\text{Ox}]}{[\text{Red}]}.$$

If the oxidant and reductant undergo ionisation into H^+ and an anion, the equation has to be modified thus:

$$E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{F} \cdot p_{\text{H}^+} + \frac{RT}{2F} \cdot \log \frac{[\text{Ox}]}{[\text{Red}]} + \frac{RT}{2F} \log \frac{1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_0}}{1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_r}}.$$

where K_0 is the dissociation constant of the oxidant and K_r , the dissociation constant of the reductant. Early workers reported extremely discordant results. Thus Green⁶, Karrer⁷, Laki⁸ reported values of potentials given by the reductant alone, which are, therefore, thermodynamically meaningless. The difficulties that have been encountered in measuring the reversible potential of this system are due to the fact that the system is electromotively sluggish and that it requires complete elimination of last traces of oxygen from the electrode surface and the solution. Borsook and co-workers^{9, 10} with the aid of special vacuum technique have been able to obtain reproducible values of reversible potentials. The difficulties due to instability of

dehydroascorbic acid have been unnecessarily exaggerated. We have found for instance that if ascorbic acid is oxidised by bromine water, and the resulting solution kept in buffer mixtures, whose p_n did not exceed 7.5 for 3 hours in contact with air, it is possible to recover the whole of the ascorbic acid by treatment with sulphuretted hydrogen

We have applied to this system the technique of measuring thermodynamic redox potentials which were developed in connection with our studies of the potential of sulphhydryl bodies.^{16, 17} The essence of the process consists in subjecting the solution of the oxidant to cathodic reduction on the surface of an electrode for some time thereby removing simultaneously the last traces of oxygen from the surface of the electrode and the bulk of the solution, and then measuring the steady potential attained by this electrode when pure nitrogen has been passed through the solution for several hours. The experimental arrangement is shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1.

A - Nitrogen inlet; B - Connection with the cathode; C - For withdrawal of solution from the cell for analysis; D - Decinormal calomel electrode; E - Siphon tube for connection between anode and cathode; F - Nitrogen outlet dipping in a water-trap; G - Anode chamber; H - Water-bath at constant temperature; I - Reaction cell-cathode chamber; J - Cotton-plug bulbs; K - Alkaline pyrogallol; L - Jena gas filter.

Buffered solutions of ascorbic acid were partially oxidised by means of bromine, and introduced into the cathode chamber (I) and the anode chamber (G), which were connected together by the agar bridge (E). A current of 10 milliampers for an hour was used for complete removal of oxygen and partial reduction of dehydroascorbic acid. A current of nitrogen was then passed through the cathode chamber for 6 hours, and the steady potential of the electrode in this chamber was measured against the decinormal calomel electrode (D). The ratio of ascorbic to dehydroascorbic acid in the solution was measured by pipetting out a part of the solution through (C) and analysing it iodometrically. E_0 has the value -0.384 at 30° and the thermodynamic equation is valid within the p_H range 2.5 and 7.5. Ball¹¹ has just reported a change in the slope of the e. m. f and p_H curve in the neighbourhood of p_H 5. We have not observed this anomaly. Nor is this anomaly to be expected if the dissociation constants of ascorbic acid and dehydroascorbic acid are of the same order of magnitude, as has been actually found to be the case.

The molecular conductivity of pure ascorbic acid¹² has been determined at various dilutions and the first dissociation constant has been found to be 6.3×10^{-5} . Birch and Harris¹³ have also obtained similar values of dissociation constant from potentiometric titration curves. Ascorbic acid does not undergo opening of the lactone ring on addition of the first equivalent of alkali. One of the enolic hydroxyls in the ring system must, therefore, be responsible for the production of H^+ ions. Feiser and Feiser¹⁴ have shown that 2-hydroxy-1:4-naphthoquinone, which has got a similar ring structure, gives a value of dissociation constant almost identical with that of ascorbic acid. Studies by Reichstein, Haworth and collaborators^{15, 15a} on the action of limited quantities of diazomethane on ascorbic acid have shown that the enolic group at position 3 has the greater acidity. The addition of one equivalent of alkali to ascorbic acid (rotation $+24^\circ$) gives a product (II) which has a molecular rotation of $+115^\circ$. The first ionisation, therefore, increases the rotation by 91° . If the rotation is observed immediately after adding a second equivalent of alkali, it is found to be $+200^\circ$ approximately. This almost equal increment in the value of molecular rotation lends support to the view that the immediate action of the second equivalent of alkali is to ionise the hydrogen atom of the second hydroxyl group without opening the lactone ring. This form (III) having molecular rotation of $+200^\circ$ is extremely unstable and tautomerises with the opening of the lactone ring into a form (IV) which has a molecular rotation of $+130^\circ$. It may be noted that on addition of two equivalents of HCl the original ascorbic acid is recovered. The equilibrium between the lactone and open-chain form in presence of OH^- according to equation,

admits of quantitative estimation by the use of experimental data obtained from potentiometric titrations in the region of p_{H} between 10 and 11. This has been done and the value of the equilibrium constant is

$$K_{22} = \frac{[\text{OH}^-][\text{Monovalent lactone anion}]}{[\text{Divalent open-chain anion}]} = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ at } 27^\circ.$$

The actual experimental data is given in the Table V.

TABLE V.

0.2M-NaOH soln. Measured against normal calomel electrode at 27°. The system was thoroughly saturated with H₂. 50 C.c. of M/100-ascorbic acid titrated.

Alkali added.	F.M.F.	p_{H} .	$K \times 10^{-3}$.
2.68 c. c.	0.895	10.200	2.74
2.76	0.905	10.359	2.40
2.88	0.915	10.533	2.51*
3.03	0.923	10.667	2.45
3.51	0.942	10.983	2.59

Mean $K = 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$

N. B. * A typical calculation may be shown as follows. Taking the figures marked with an asterisk in the above table, we have, the free alkali remaining in the system at equilibrium calculated from p_{H} , 10.533 = 0.00034M

The amount of alkali added = 2.88 c. c. of which 2.5 c. c. being used up by the formation of monosodium salt, hence alkali really available for second step dissociation = 0.38 c. c. in 52.88 c. c. solution.

Conc. of alkali added = 0.0015M.

Conc. of divalent open-chain anion = 0.0015 - 0.00034M.

Conc. of monovalent lactone anion = {0.01 - (0.0015 - 0.00034)}M.

$$K = \frac{(0.00034) \times [0.01 - (0.0015 - 0.00034)]}{(0.0015 - 0.00034)} = 2.51 \times 10^{-3},$$

It is necessary to discuss the physico-chemical properties of dehydroascorbic acid at some length as our results are at considerable variance from those of Hirst, Herbert (*et al.*).¹⁸ They find that the oxidation product of ascorbic acid, newly formed by the action of I_2 , has no selective absorption band characteristic of ascorbic acid and is neutral in reaction. The latter observation is based on very doubtful evidence. We have been able to prepare solutions of dehydroascorbic acid free from association with any other electrolyte by the action of hydrogen peroxide in presence of colloidal platinum. The solution has a molecular conductivity of 33.8 at $\nu=100$, $t=23^\circ$. It has an acid reaction, almost identical with that of ascorbic acid, and its dissociation constant as determined from conductivity data is 12.6×10^{-5} . The absence of selective absorption band in the ultraviolet has led to the adoption of formula (V) for the newly formed dehydroascorbic acid which has a molecular rotation of $+56^\circ$

Perhaps this form dissociates after dehydration into anion (VI) and H^+ .

Addition of one equivalent of alkali to dehydroascorbic acid leads also to the production of anion (VI) with a molecular rotation of -26° . The proof that the lactone ring does not open at this stage is supplied by the fact that it is possible to recover ascorbic acid in 95% yield from this solution by treatment with H_2S . If to this salt solution an equivalent of mineral acid is added, a product is obtained whose molecular rotation is -10° which is practically the same as that obtained by Herbert (*et al.*), for a solution of dehydroascorbic acid three days after preparation. This old sample develops a selective absorption band in the ultraviolet almost similar to that of ascorbic acid. It appears, therefore, very probable that in an old sample of dehydroascorbic acid equilibrium exists between forms (V) and (VII) thus:

The conclusion of Hirst (*et al*), that the neutral salt is formed from dehydroascorbic acid by the opening of the lactone ring is untenable, for in that case ascorbic acid could not have been recovered by simple treatment with H₂S. On addition of excess of alkali, however, the lactone ring opens up and an open-chain anion is formed.

It has been generally accepted that dehydroascorbic acid is a monobasic acid, and that the open-chain anion has the constitution (VIII)

(VIII)

Potentiometric titrations with a strong alkali in a rapid current of hydrogen, which prevents further oxidation and rupture of the molecule, lead to different conclusions. Concordant equilibrium constants are obtained if we assume a reversible transformation of the type,

The equilibrium constant has the value 3.8×10^{-5} (approx.).

As in the case of the second step ionisation of ascorbic acid, the opening of this lactone into an open-chain divalent anion was followed from the potentiometric titration of dehydroascorbic acid. The results are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Alkali (NaOH) = 5/18 N. M/110-Dehydroascorbic acid (50 c.c.), measured against N/10-calomel electrode at 21°, saturated with H₂ gas.

Alkali added.	E. M. F.	p _H	K × 10 ⁻⁵ .
2.60	0.920	9.75	4.40
3.22	0.961	10.43	3.51
3.40	0.971	10.60	3.62
			Mean 3.6×10^{-5}

This open-chain anion can only give back ascorbic acid by treatment with concentrated HI. In alkaline media, it is a powerful reducing agent, being further oxidised in the cold by AgNO_3 , and H_2O_2 with colloidal Pt. It is very unstable and decomposes easily in presence of air into oxalic acid and *l*-threonic acid.

It is well known that *d*-ascorbic acid does not possess the biochemical properties of its optical isomer, the vitamin C. It was, therefore, worthwhile investigating more fully the anisotropic properties of the molecule. Ascorbic acid has an absorption band in the ultraviolet, the band head being at about $265 \mu\mu$. We have measured the circular dichroism, *i.e.*, the difference in the extinction coefficients for *d*- and *l*-circularly polarised light in this region by a method which has already been described in a recent issue of our Journal (1937, 14, 495).

A large difference has been observed and the results are given in Table VII.

TABLE VII₂Wave-length = $2536 \mu\mu$.

Conc. of ascorbic acid,	$g = \frac{\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1}$
0.0004M	0.0428
0.00015M	0.0373
	Mean 0.0400

The sodium salt of dehydroascorbic acid gives a pale yellow solution, which shows circular dichroism even in the greenish blue region. A monochromatic plane polarised beam of light on passing through such a solution, becomes elliptically polarised due to differential absorption of the two oppositely circularly polarised components. The experimental results are given in Table VIII.

It is clear that several hydrogen atoms in the molecule are extremely labile. They are responsible for easy dehydrogenation and the numerous stepwise ionisation of the molecule. These changes on closer examination appear to be of a protein character and much patient investigation will be necessary before the nature of these complex transformations are completely cleared up.

TABLE VIII.

Measurement of rotatory dispersion and ellipticity of dehydroascorbic acid as determined by Bruhat's apparatus (Bull. Soc. chim., 1930, iv, 47, 251) in the visible region^a.

Conc. of dehydroascorbic acid (to which had been added 3 equivalents of caustic soda) = $M/100$.

Wave-length.	Length of the soln.	Rotation.	Sp. rotation.	Ellipticity.	$\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2$, calc. from eq. ^a	Mol. extn. coeff. ϵ_2 .	ρ (Anisotropic factor).
6498 Å	20 cm.	-0'06	-17°
6400	"	-0'06	-17°
6300	"	-0'07	-20°
5760	"	-0'07	-20°
5460	"	-0'08	-22°
5300	5 cm.	-0'03	-34°
4958	2 cm.	-0'01 ?	...	-0'03 (right handed)	0'045	10.7	0'0042
4798	"	-0'01 ?	...	-0'04 (")	0'06	15	0'004
4538	1 cm.	?	...	-0'02 (")	0'06	23.7	0'0025

^a Ellipticity = ρ (in radians) = $\frac{[\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2] \cdot c \cdot l}{4 \times 0.4943}$; c = Molar conc.; l = length in cm.

R E F E R E N C E S.

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